

AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
DIGITAL CLOCK AND CALENDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
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ABSTRACT

The design and operational principle of the digital calendar and digital clock is the subject of this thesis. The system as realized in this book is made up of six units.

The power supply unit supplies the required regulated voltage to the appropriate connections of the overall circuit. The micro controller controls the general operation of the circuit; all the other units are interfaced to it. The input unit is activated by pressing the keypad (buttons) unit to call up the subroutine program that controls the set date, month, year and time with alarm instructions. The decoder with the aid of the micro controller executes the instruction codes, which are transmitted to the light emitting diode that corresponds to the actual day that is to display. The display unit consist of a twelve seven segment display in which their common anode is driven by a NPN switching transistor; displaying digits in a multiplex mode.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this project is to produce a narrative description of the design and construction of digital calendar with date, month, year and time with alarm.

Firstly computer aided design is the modeling of physical system on Computers allowing both interactive and automatic analysis of design variant and the expression of design in a form suitable for manufacturing. This follows by explaining digital calendar/clock as a date/time keeping digital device which is fast gaining wide acceptance and application in the present days due to its ability to provide a very high precision timing by the days and events. Digital calendar can also be described as digital system for processing information in which the information is represented by physical quantities, which are so constrained to take only discrete values that can be referred to as binary signals.

The application of digital calendar with clock varies widely from normal time alarm system. Also computer system uses digital clock and calendar in keeping track of time and date in synchronization of several activities in its everyday operation due to the abilities in the systems.

In this design we have implored the use of both hardware and software to bring about the entire project. The hardware components are solely coordinated by

the AT89C51 micro controller chip while the c programming language is used to program the chip

1.1 Objective of the project design

This project (digital calendar with date, month, year and time) is based on a computer aided design. It enables anybody to read both time and date from the clock and calendars respectively. This project can serve in any aspect of life. It encourages the following:

- Proper reading of time and date
- Prompt keeping of appointments
- Proper simulation and utilization of time
- Proper management, etc.

This project is design in such a way that if sold in the market, the buyer gets as much service from the calendar which is tantamount to the resources he paid for it. This project can be kept or used in houses, cars etc as a time/date device.

The features of the AT89C51 were exploited to achieve the desired sequence of operation of this project.

With the AT89C51, we were able to see how the output /input devices were solely coordinated through the software program that was written to the chip with the aid of an EPROM programmer using C programming language.

1.2 Justification of the project

Micro controller base design on digital calendar is an improvement in the electronics sector. Electronics like this device can be coupled solely via the use of discrete components including counter, multiplexers, de-multiplexers, timers and latches; moreover the use of a micro controller for this design can be justified by the reduction in the number of components used in the course of the design which also improves the reliability durability and flexibility.

1.3 Scope of project

The construction of a computer-aided design of a digital clock with calendar is implemented using micro controller based on discrete components like transistors, resistors, LED, seven segment display etc.

Micro controller was used in this work and not only hardware, in order to allow for easy flexibility and low level of errors. The project was made portable and also there is provision for a back up battery, if a.c supply fails. Since the time and

date keeping devices are very imperative to the society, so this project has been designed to solve the predicaments of irregular date and time keeping.

1.4 Block diagram

Fig. 1.1 System Block Diagram

From the figure above, the microcontroller is seen at the centre of design receiving the input as well as output to the other peripheral components. The block diagrams consist of six stages, which are:

1. Keypad unit

These are soft touch buttons mounted on the front of the casing from which input signal is sent to the microcontroller unit to either set the calendar, time or the alarm unit.

2. Microcontroller (AT89C51):

This is an integrated circuit programmed with an EPROM programmer to receive input signals and relating it to other interfaced sub-unit attached to it for their corresponding signals generation.

3. Display unit

The display unit consists of the light emitting diodes and power transistors design to sink current to the light emitting diode (LED). It is necessary to have these power transistors because the micro controller cannot produce the large current needed by the circuit. The transistor is configured in the switch mode in order to achieve this purpose.

In this block diagram the led are arrange to display the days in the week and also arrange in the seven segment to display time and calendar.

4. Alarm unit

This unit is made up of the buzzer and the alarm indicator. The alarm indicator light when the alarm is set by the depressing of the alarm set button.

5. Decoder unit

The unit is made up of the DM74LS138 three to eight line decoder which receive input signal from the microcontroller via pin 1,2,3 and sends this input signal to the output pins displaying days.

6. Power supply unit

The transformer, bridge rectifier diodes, capacitors and a voltage regulator make up the power supply unit. This power unit gives out an output voltage of +5v.

1.5 Project report organization

This report is structured to follow the origin of the digital calendar in all through the design and implementation phase. The report takes into account the step-by-step process followed in order to arrive at the final design.

The report is broken into Chapters each handling a specific aspect of the microcontroller based digital calendar system.

Chapter one of this report introduces the concept of the digital calendar and its objectives. Chapter two centers on the Literature review, the origin and history of digital calendar and its basic uses. Chapter Three explains the components, which makes up the digital calendar and their basic functionalities/mode of operation.

Chapter Four discusses how the system was implemented while Chapter Five and Six handles the concluding part of the design: system testing and integration, data testing, Summary and Conclusion.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

The digital calendar with date, month, year and time is designed to be hung in offices, rooms, churches and even car dashboard, where time and date can be easily accessed.

2.1 Origin of project

There can be little doubt that the first clock appeared shortly after 1500, when Peter Heinlain, a black smith in Nurberg Germany introduced main spring as a replacement for weights in driving clocks. Early clocks were made in Germany and at Blois in France. This early timepiece measured some 4 to 5 inches (100 to 125mm) in diameter and about 3 inches (75mm) in depth. They were carried about in hand.

One of the main defect of the early clocks was greater when fully wound than when it was almost run down since the time/date keeping of a clock fitted with a verge escapement is greatly influenced by the force driving it, this problem was quite serious. Solution of the problem was advanced between 1515 and 1540 by the invention by Jacob the Czech of praque, of the fuse, a coned shaped groove

pulley used together with a barrel containing the mainspring is made to rotate a barrel in which it is housed.

The most famous English clock/calendar maker of his time, who is known for clock making improvement, was Tampion Thomas.

Tampion made an early repealing clock with calendar a type that could be made to sound the nearest hour and nearest quarter hour by pushing two pieces extending from the side of the clock. Tampion devised improvement in pendulum and he constructed several clocks made to run for a year without rewinding.

The progressive miniaturization of electronics components in the 20th century made possible the development of all electronic clocks with calendar. The complex circuits of such clocks with calendar (digital) enable them to vary the time/date keeping functions and also made possible digital readouts of the time/date in place of the traditional second minutes and hour hands.

2.2 Uses of project

In this project the techniques employed makes time/date reading extremely easy and convenient. And this is achieved by the use of software and hardware implementation or design.

The whole system has been proved to be very reliable since date/time can easily be read as digits in the display unit. And the time and date settings can be adjusted using the keypad buttons.

Digital calendar with time is a date and time keeping digital device, which is fast gaining wider acceptance and application in the present days due to its ability to provide a every high precision timing of the day and events.

CHAPTER THREE

DESIGN ANALYSIS

Designing the system was the major part of this project work and this involved the planning and estimation of the entire system before the actual implementation. Here, every component used is accounted for and resolved to obtain the best performance.

3.1 Information gathering: These are different ways in which information's are gotten for the project; these includes:

Library research: In the course of designing this project data over a wide range of topics relating to the project was obtained from the library, topics such as seven-segment display, decoder circuits, micro controller circuits and application etc were also obtained from the library.

Internet browsing: This is one of the highest sources of data collection for the project. In depth study of the project historical background, up to date information on designs and applications were also obtained. Tutorials on the project were also present in some websites.

Special directives and training: This is the information gotten from stone code inc., here lectures on how to program the microcontroller were received. Their

machine was used to burn the written software program into the microcontroller. The project supervisor also gave directives/focus with respect to the scope of the project.

3.2 Analysis of block diagram

Fig. 3.1 Block diagram of project

3.1.1 Keypad unit

It consists of the following:

1. Time set button: It enables adjustment to be made on the time display.
2. Date set button: To adjust date
3. Enter key button: It is used to activate whenever as adjustment is made on the display.
4. Up and down button: For increment or decrement of time and date during settings.
5. Alarm set button: For setting of alarm when necessary

P1.7 of the micro controller connects the alarm set switch through the $10K\Omega$ resistor, which connects to the one terminal of the button the ground. And the other terminal of the resistor is connected to Vcc.

P3.6 of micro controller connects to the set date.

P3.7 of Micro controller connects to the set time

P3.0 of micro controller connects to the increment button

P0.7 of micro controller connects to the decrement button

P3.1 of micro controller connects to the enter button

P3.6, P3.7, P3.0, P0.7, and P3.1 have the same connection as explained in P1.7

above. Therefore, this is illustrated on the figure below

Fig. 3.2 Microcontroller interface with keypad

3.1.2 Power supply unit

The power supply circuit is made up of 240/12Vac bridge rectifier, capacitor (2200uf) and a +5Vdc voltage regulator (7805).

The a.c voltage is rectified to d.c voltage with bridge rectifier, and the voltage regulator regulates the 12Vdc to 5Vdc which is the required voltage for the microcontroller referred to fig. 3.3

Fig. 3.3 Power supply interface with microcontroller

3.1.3 Alarm unit

This consists of an LED, which connects from the P2.7 of the micro controller, which in turn connects to 4.7K Ω resistor, which finally connects to the VCC. The LED indicates on the alarm is set to slow.

P2.6 of the micro controller connects to the resistor (2K Ω), through the base of the transistor (NPN C, 945) and the collector to the ground, while the emitter terminal is connected to the negative terminal of the alarm speaker, and the positive to the Vcc. The remaining terminal of the resistor to Vcc, as shown in the figure 3.4

Fig. 3.4 Micro controller interface with alarm unit

3.1.4 Display unit

The display unit is made up of: -

- (1) Seven segment display unit which comprises of 12, seven segment display capable of displaying time in hours, minutes and second and date in day, month and year.
- (2) Weekly display unit, which comprises of a 3-8 line decoder, 7 light emitting diodes which represent Sunday to Saturday respectively. All the corresponding

segments of the 12 seven segment displays are connected together which in turn connect to the micro controller.

All the anodes of the seven segment LEDs are internally connected together and brought out to Vcc, which is connected to the emitter of the switching transistor (NPN C 945), and its collector is connected to the Vcc, and its base is then connected to our terminal of $4.7K\lambda$ resistor which in turn is connected from the microcontroller. So remaining terminal of the $2K\Omega$ resistor is connected to the VCC.

On the weekly display unit, the micro controller sends binary codes through the inputs the 3-8-line decoder IC (74LS138) that decodes it to the appropriate binary code equivalent, which will be indicated by the LED on the day. It corresponds. Also pin 4,5 & 8 of the IC are connected to the ground while pin 16 is connected to the Vcc.

3.2 Analysis of AT89C51 microcontroller

The AT89C51 is a low power, high performance cmos 8-bit microcomputer with 4Kbytes of flash programmable and erasable read only memory (PEROM). The device is manufactured using Atmel`s high density nonvolatile memory technology and is compatible with the industry standard MCS-51 instruction set and pinout. The on-chip flash allows the program memory to be reprogrammed in system or by a conventional nonvolatile memory programmer. By combining a versatile 8-bit CPU with flash on a monolithic chip, the Atmel AT89C51 is a powerful microcomputer, which provides a highly flexible and cost effective solution to many embedded control application.

The AT89C51 is designed with static logic for operation down to zero frequency and support two software selectable power saving modes. The idle mode stops the CPU while allowing the RAM, timer/counters, serial port and interrupt system to continue functioning. The power down mode saves the RAM contents but freezes the oscillator disabling all other chip functions until the next hardware reset [4].

Fig. 3.6 Pin configuration of AT89C51

3.3.1 Features of AT89C51

- Programmable serial channel
- Compatible with MCS-51TM product
- 4Kbytes of in-system Reprogrammables flash memory - Endurance: 1,000 write/Erase cycles
- Fully static operation:0Hz to 24MHz

- Three-level program memory lock
- 128 x 8-bit internal RAM
- 32 programmable I/O lines
- Two 16-bit timer/counters
- Six interrupt sources
- Low-power idle and power-down modes.

Fig. 3.7 Block diagram of AT89C51 internal circuitry

3.3.2 Pin description

V_{cc}

Supply voltage.

GND

Ground.

Port 0

Port 0 is an 8-bit open-drain bi-directional I/O port. As an output port, each pin can sink eight TTL inputs. When 1s are written to port 0 pins, the pins can be used as high impedance inputs. Port 0 may also be configured to be the multiplexed low order

Address/data bus during accesses to external program and data memory. In this mode P0 has internal pull-ups. Port 0 also receives the code bytes during Flash programming, and outputs the code bytes during program verification. External pull-ups are required during program verification.

Port 1

Port 1 is an 8-bit bi-directional I/O port with internal pull-ups. The Port 1 output buffers can sink/source four TTL inputs. When 1s are written to Port 1 pins they are pulled high by the internal pull-ups and can be used as inputs. As inputs, Port 1 pins that are externally being pulled low will source current (IIL) because of the internal pull-ups. Port 1 also receives the low-order address bytes during Flash programming and verification.

Port 2

Port 2 is an 8-bit bi-directional I/O port with internal pull-ups. The Port 2 output buffers can sink/source four TTL inputs. When 1s are written to Port 2 pins they are pulled high by the internal pull-ups and can be used as inputs. As inputs, Port 2 pins that are externally being pulled low will source current (IIL) because of the internal pull-ups. Port 2 emits the high-order address byte during fetches from external program memory and during accesses to external data memory that uses 16-bit addresses (MOVX @ DPTR). In this application, it uses strong internal pull-ups when emitting 1s. During accesses to external data memory that uses 8-bit addresses (MOVX @ RI), Port 2 emits the contents of the P2 Special Function Register.

Port 2 also receives the high-order address bits and some control signals during Flash programming and verification.

Port 3

Port 3 is an 8-bit bi-directional I/O port with internal pull-ups. The Port 3 output buffers can sink/source four TTL inputs. When 1s are written to Port 3 pins they are pulled high by the internal pull-ups and can be used as inputs. As inputs,

Port 3 pins that are externally being pulled low will source current (IIL) because of the pull-ups. Port 3 also serves the functions of various special features of the AT89C51 as listed below.

Table 3.1 Alternate functions of port 3

Port Pin	Alternate Functions
P3.0	RXD (serial input port)
P3.1	TXD (serial output port)
P3.2	$\overline{\text{INT0}}$ (external interrupt 0)
P3.3	$\overline{\text{INT1}}$ (external interrupt 1)
P3.4	T0 (timer 0 external input)
P3.5	T1 (timer 1 external input)
P3.6	$\overline{\text{WR}}$ (external data memory write strobe)
P3.7	$\overline{\text{RD}}$ (external data memory read strobe)

Port 3 also receives some control signals for Flash programming and verification.

RST

Reset input. A high on this pin for two machine cycles while the oscillator is running resets the device.

ALE/PROG

Address Latch Enable output pulse for latching the low byte of the address during accesses to external memory. This pin is also the program pulse input (PROG) during Flash programming. In normal operation ALE is emitted at a constant rate of 1/6 the oscillator frequency, and may be used for external timing or clocking

purposes. Note, however, that one ALE pulse is skipped during each access to external Data Memory. If desired, ALE operation can be disabled by setting bit 0 of SFR location 8EH. With the bit set, ALE is active only during a MOVX or MOVC instruction. Otherwise, the pin is weakly pulled high. Setting the ALE-disable bit has no effect if the microcontroller is in external execution mode.

PSEN

Program Store Enable is the read strobe to external program memory. When the AT89C51 is executing code from external program memory, PSEN is activated twice each machine cycle, except that two PSEN activations are skipped during each access to external data memory.

EA/VPP

External Access Enable. EA must be strapped to GND in order to enable the device to fetch code from external program memory locations starting at 0000H up to FFFFH.

Note, however, that if lock bit 1 is programmed, EA will be internally latched on reset. EA should be strapped to VCC for internal program executions. This pin

also receives the 12-volt programming enable voltage (VPP) during Flash programming, for parts that require 12-volt VPP.

XTAL1

Input to the inverting oscillator amplifier and input to the internal clock operating circuit.

XTAL2

Output from the inverting oscillator amplifier.

3.4 Light emitting diode(LED) characteristics

As the name indicates, it is a forward-biased P-N junction which emits visible light when energised. The colour of the emitted light depends on the type of material used as given below

- GaAs- Infrared radiation (invisible)
- GaP- Red or green light
- GaAsP- Red or yellow (amber) light

LEDs that emit blue light are also available but red is the most common. LEDs emit no light when reverse biased.

LEDs are manufactured with domed lenses in order to lessen the reabsorption problem ; they are always encased in order to protect their delicate wires. Being made of semiconductor material, it is rugged and has a life of more than 10,000 hours.

Since LEDs operate at voltage levels from 1.5v to 3.3v, they are highly compatible with solid state circuitry [2].

LED Seven segment display

This type of display comes in a variety of colours, sizes and packaging styles. While red is still the most favored colour, green, yellow and orange LED readouts are also available. The readouts come packaged in standard DIP configurations with clear or modified diffused lens – the latter, for “Full-flood” visibility.

Its mode of fabrication is based in either a common-cathode or common-anode arrangement. But common – anode arrangement was used in this project for easier configuration. The seven-segment display gets its name from the fact seven illuminated segments are used to configure the digits 0-9 (and a few lower and upper case letters). Its arrangement is in the figure of number eight. It's read out and list of segments required for it to illuminate is given below.

In common cathode, all the cathode are internally tied together and brought out to circuit ground through an external current limiting, or pull-down resistor. A high voltage to an individual anode turns the LED segment “ON”.

Also, in common anode arrangement all anodes are internally connected and brought out to + Vcc through an external current limiting, or pull-up resistor. A low voltage to any LED cathode turns it on [3]. As read out, LED display offers two distinct advantages, which are as follows:

Allows digital designers maximum flexibility due to their sizes and shapes.

They are visible in subdued light.

But operation of LED in bright light (out door displays) makes the display to be washed off by direct sunlight (invisible). The diagram of the seven segment display is shown below.

SEVEN SEGMENT DISPLAY

DIFFERENT COLOURS

OF LED

LAYOUT

Internal Circuitry Of The Two Types Seven Segment Display

Fig. 3.8 Seven segment Display and LED

3.5 Analysis of voltage regulator

Voltage Regulator (also called a "regulator") has only three legs and appears to be a comparatively simple device but it is actually a very complex integrated circuit [1]. A regulator converts varying input voltage and produces a constant

"regulated" output voltage. Voltage regulators are available in a variety of outputs, typically 5 volts, 9 volts and 12 volts. The last two digits in the name indicate the output voltage.

Fig. 3.9 A 7805 Voltage regulator

After rectification we have full 15v on the positive end and to obtain the 5v required to drive the microcontroller a voltage regulator (LM7805) is connected to the circuit. This particular type of voltage regulator ensures that only 5v passes through to the other side. Hence, the above power supply design of the system can operate on +5v and +15v as well as 0v level.

3.6 Analysis of voltage supply transformer

The voltage transformer is a device that step-up or step-down the input voltage to the specified voltage which is determined by the turns ratio of the primary and secondary side [1]. In this case we are considering a step-down mode configuration. Due to the large current drain by the LED display, our secondary current I_2 is made sufficient enough to supply the demanded current.

Fig. 3.10 Circuit diagram of step down transformer

Transformer Equation

$$E_1/E_2 = N_1/N_2 = I_2/I_1$$

Where E = Voltage

N = No of turns

I = current

Numbers 1 =primary, 2 = secondary

3.7 Analysis of power transistor (i.e. LED drivers)

A power transistor is a bipolar junction formed by joining three sections of some conductor materials, each with a different doping concentration. The three sections can be either a thin n region sandwiched between p and p+ layers, or a p region between n and n+ layers where the superscript “plus” indicates more heavily doped materials. The resulting BJTs are called pnp and npn transistors respectively [3].

Fig. 3.11 Bipolar junction transistor

The operation of the NPN power BJT may be explained by considering the transistor as consisting of two back-to-back PN junctions. The base (b) junction acts very much like a diode when it is forward-biased, thus, one can picture the corresponding flow of hole and electron current from base to emitter when the

collector is open and the BE junction is forward biased [5].

3.8 System flow chart

CHAPTER FOUR

DESIGN OF PROJECT

4.1 Preliminary Design

Fig. 4.1 Block Diagram Overview

4.2.1 Power Supply Design

There are many types of power supply. Most are designed to convert high voltage AC mains electricity to a suitable low voltage supply for electronics circuits and other devices [1]. A power supply can be broken down into a series of blocks, each of which performs a particular function.

For example a 5V regulated supply:

Fig. 4.2 Block Diagram of Regulated Power Supply System

Each of the blocks is described in more detail below:

- Transformer - steps down high voltage AC mains to low voltage AC.
- Rectifier - converts AC to DC, but the DC output is varying.
- Smoothing - smoothes the DC from varying greatly to a small ripple.
- Regulator - eliminates ripple by setting DC output to a fixed voltage.

Power supplies made from these blocks are described below with a circuit diagram and a graph of their output:

- Transformer only
- Transformer + Rectifier
- Transformer + Rectifier + Smoothing
- Transformer + Rectifier + Smoothing + Regulator

Step Down Transformer

Fig. 4.3 Step Down Transformer

The low voltage AC output is suitable for lamps, heaters and special AC motors. It is not suitable for electronic circuits unless they include a rectifier and a smoothing capacitor [6].

Transformer + Rectifier

The varying DC output is suitable for lamps, heaters and standard motors. It is not suitable for electronic circuits unless they include a smoothing capacitor.

Transformer + Rectifier + Smoothing

The smooth DC output has a small ripple. It is suitable for most electronic circuits.

Transformer + Rectifier + Smoothing + Regulator

The regulated DC output is very smooth with no ripple. It is suitable for all electronic circuits.

4.2.2 Micro-Controller

From the circuit diagram below, an overview of the connection of the various components can be explained. Thus the 10uf/16v capacitor was connected to the reset pin and pulled high to +5v. This is to enable the microcontroller to reset itself as power is switched on. The reset pin requires a logic 1 to reset and at start up the capacitor acts as a short circuit and charges up within seconds ($t=RC$) via the resistor keeping the reset key at logic zero.

The microcontroller also requires a clock input of 16 MHz generated by the crystal oscillator.

Port 1, 2, 3 and 0 were used for interfacing; Port 1 (pin 1-7) and Port 0 (pin 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39) were connected to the calendar and time display segments a, b, c, d, e, f, and g of the seven segment display. The segments of the

seven segment receives a logic signal of either 1 or 0 from the microcontroller. In Port 2, pin 21, 22, 23, 24, 25 and 26 were used as output pins to drive the switching transistors of the individual anodes of the time and calendar segment. Port 2 (pin 27 and 28) to switch on the alarm and the LED to indicate alarm set. Port 3 (pin 13, 14, 15) are used to send logic signals to the input select of the 3-8 line decoder (pin 1, 2, 3).

Resistor Values Analysis for the seven segment display

Each segment LED of the seven segment has a maximum current tolerance of 30mA; assuming the maximum current I am working with is 23mA then

$V=IR$ where $V=5V$ and $I=23mA$

$$R=V/I= 5/23*10^{-3}=217\Omega.$$

This value is closer to the 220Ω resistor used.

4.2.3 Transistorized Seven Segment Driver

Fig. 4.4 A transistorized seven segment

The NPN transistor is use as a switch to switch on the corresponding anode of each segment .The segment is design to use a current sink of about 23mA. The npn transistor from data book has the following limiting values in accordance with the absolute maximum rating system (IEC134).

Table 4.1 Limiting values of NPN transistor: C945

SYMBOL	CONDITIONS	MIN.	MAX.	UNIT
V_{CBO}	OPEN EMITTER	-----	60	V
V_{CEO}	OPEN BASE	-----	50	V
V_{EBO}	OPEN COLLECTOR	-----	5	V
I_C		-----	100	mA
I_{CM}		-----	200	mA
I_{BM}		-----	100	mA
h_{f_E}		-----	120	

Analysis;

Maximum current from port 1, 2, 3 of the microcontroller is 15mA. The transistor is design to sink a minimum current of 2.5mA, therefore from OHMS LAW

$V=IR$ where $V=5v$, $I=2.5mA$, $R=?$

$$R = V/I, 5/2.5 = 2 \text{ K}\Omega.$$

The resistor value connected to the base of the collector is $2\text{k}\Omega$.

4.3.1 Software Design

Fig. 4.5 Software Design

4.3.2 Program Code

```
#include "at89x51.h"
```

```
code unsigned char
```

```
digit[16]={0x40,0x79,0x24,0x30,0x19,0x12,0x02,0x78,0,0x10,0x08,0x03,0x46,0x21,0x06,0x0e};
```

```
code unsigned int
```

```
dec[]={0x0,0x1,0x2,0x3,0x4,0x5,0x6,0x7,0x8,0x9,0x10,0x11,0x12,0x13,0x14,0x15,0x16,0x17,0x18,0x19,0x20,0x21,0x22,0x23,0x24,0x25,0x26,0x27,0x28,0x29,0x30,0x31,0x32,0x33,0x34,0x35,0x36,0x37,0x38,0x39,0x40,0x41,0x42,0x43,0x44,0x45,0x46,0x47,0x48,0x49,0x50,0x51,0x52,0x53,0x54,0x55,0x56,0x57,0x58,0x59,0x60,0x61,0x62,0x63,0x64,0x65,0x66,0x67,0x68,0x69,0x70,0x71,0x72,0x73,0x74,0x75,0x76,0x77,0x78,0x79,0x80,0x81,0x82,0x83,0x84,0x85,0x86,0x87,0x88,0x89,0x90,0x91,0x92,0x93,0x94,0x95,0x96,0x97,0x98,0x99}
```

```
};
```

```
volatile unsigned char
```

```
buffer,buffer2,display_buffer1,display_buffer3,display_buffer4,display_buffer5
```

```
;
```

```
volatile unsigned char
```

```
display_buffer2,display_buffer6,display_buffer7,i,x,y,show;
```

```
volatile unsigned char data1,data2,data3,data4,set_pos,disp_pos;
```

```
volatile char day_name;
```

```
bit flag,flag1,over;
```

```
char sec,min,year,hour,day,month;
```

```
unsigned int del;
```

```
//delay function:
```

```
void delay(int pause)
```

```
{
```

```
while (!(pause==0))
```

```
{
```

```
    pause--;
```

```

_asm;          // 1ms assembly code(for 18Mhz crystal)

mov r6,#3     // adjust to crystal frequency

mov r7,#215

00111$:

djnz r7,00111$

djnz r6,00111$

_endasm;

}

}

//;;;;;;;;;;;;;Display Functin;;;;;;;;;;;;;

void display(void) interrupt 1

{

TR0=0;        //disable timer

if((del>400)&&(disp_pos==0)){

    del=1;

    //=====running the normal clock loop=====

```

```
sec++;

if(sec==60){
    sec=0;
    min++;
    if(min==60){
        min=0;
        hour++;

        if(hour==12){
            hour=0;
            //hour=0;
            flag1 = !flag1;

            day++;

            if(++day_name==7)day_name = 0;

            switch(month){
```

```
//jan  
  
case 1:  
  
if(day==32){  
  
    day=1;  
  
    month++;}  
  
    break;
```

```
//feb  
  
case 2:  
  
if((year%4)==0){  
  
    if(day==30){  
  
        day=1;  
  
        month++;}  
  
        break;  
  
    }  
  
    else{  
  
        if(day==29){  
  
            day=1;
```

```
        month++;}

    }

    break;

//mar

case 3:

if(day==32){

    day=1;

    month++;}

    break;

//apr

case 4:

if(day==31){

    day=1;

    month++;}

    break;
```

```
//may  
case 5:  
if(day==32){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
break;
```

```
//june  
case 6:  
if(day==31){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
break;
```

```
//july  
case 7:  
if(day==32){  
    day=1;
```

```
        month++;}

        break;

//aug

case 8:

if(day==32){

        day=1;

        month++;}

        break;

//sep

case 9:

if(day==31){

        day=1;

        month++;}

        break;

//oct
```

```
case 10:  
if(day==32){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
break;
```

```
//nov
```

```
case 11:  
if(day==31){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
break;
```

```
//dec
```

```
case 12:  
if(day==32){  
    day=1;  
    month=1;  
    year++;
```

```
if(year==100)year=0;
```

```
break;
```

```
default:
```

```
break;
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
if(i>5){
```

```
display_buffer1=dec[year];
```

```
display_buffer2=dec[month];
```

```
display_buffer3=dec[day];
```

```
display_buffer5=dec[sec];
```

```
display_buffer6=dec[min];
```

```
display_buffer7=dec[hour];
```

```
i=0;}
```

```
switch(i){
```

```
case 0:
```

```
P2_5=0;
```

```
buffer=display_buffer1 & 0x0f;
```

```
// show first character
```

```
if(flag&&(disp_pos!=1)){P1=0x3f;}
```

```
else{P1=digit[buffer];}
```

```

        buffer=display_buffer5 & 0x0f;           // show p first
character

        if(flag&&(disp_pos!=4)){P0=0x3f;}

        else{P0=digit[buffer];}

        P2_0=1;

        break;

        case 1:

        P2_0=0;

        buffer=(display_buffer1>>4) & 0x0f;     // show second character

        if(flag&&(disp_pos!=1)){P1=0x3f;}

        else{P1=digit[buffer];}

        buffer=(display_buffer5>>4) & 0x0f;     // show second character

        if(flag&&(disp_pos!=4)){P0=0x3f;}

        else{P0=digit[buffer];}

        P2_1=1;

```

```
break;

case 2:

P2_1=0;

buffer=display_buffer2 & 0x0f;           // show first character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=2)){P1=0x3f;}

else{P1=digit[buffer];}

buffer=display_buffer6 & 0x0f;           // show p first
character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=5)){P0=0x3f;}

else{P0=digit[buffer];}

P2_2=1;

break;

case 3:

P2_2=0;
```

```
buffer=(display_buffer2>>4) & 0x0f; // show second character
```

```
if(flag&&(disp_pos!=2)){P1=0x3f;}
```

```
else{P1=digit[buffer];}
```

```
buffer=(display_buffer6>>4) & 0x0f; // show second character
```

```
if(flag&&(disp_pos!=5)){P0=0x3f;}
```

```
else{P0=digit[buffer];}
```

```
P2_3=1;
```

```
break;
```

```
case 4:
```

```
P2_3=0;
```

```
buffer=display_buffer3 & 0x0f; // show first character
```

```
if(flag&&(disp_pos!=3)){P1=0x3f;}
```

```
else{P1=digit[buffer];}
```

```
buffer=display_buffer7 & 0x0f; // show p first
```

```
character
```

```
if(flag&&(disp_pos!=6)){P0=0x3f;}

else{P0=digit[buffer];}

P2_4=1;

break;

case 5:

P2_4=0;

buffer=(display_buffer3>>4) & 0x0f;           // show second character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=3)){P1=0x3f;}

else{P1=digit[buffer];}

buffer=(display_buffer7>>4) & 0x0f;           // show second character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=6)){P0=0x3f;}

else{P0=digit[buffer];}

P2_5=1;

break;
```

```

    default:

    break;

}

    i++; del++;

TH0=180;                // load timer

TL0=240;

TR0=1;                 //enable timer

}

void main(void){

    TMOD=0; //choose timer mode

    ET0=1;             //enable timer interupt

    EA=1;              //enable global interupt

    TR0=1;             //run timer

    flag=flag1=i=0;   //intitalize variables

```

```
del=1;set_pos=disp_pos=0;day_name = 1;

sec=00;min=16;hour=10;day=17;month=12;year=11;

//P0=P1=x=0;

while(1){

    if(!P3_3){

        delay(30);

        if(!P3_3){

            switch(disp_pos){

                case 1:

                    if(++year > 99)year=06;

                    break;

                case 2:

                    if(++month>12)month=1;

                    break;

                case 3:
```

```
if(++day>31)day=1;
```

```
if(++day_name==7)day_name = 0;
```

```
break;
```

```
case 4:
```

```
if(++sec > 59)sec=0;
```

```
break;
```

```
case 5:
```

```
if(++min > 59)min=0;
```

```
break;
```

```
case 6:
```

```
if(++hour > 12)hour=1;flag1=!flag1;
```

```
break;
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
while(!P3_3){;}
```

```
}
```

```
if(!P3_4){
```

```
    delay(30);
```

```
    if(!P3_4){
```

```
        switch(dispos){
```

```
            case 1:
```

```
                if(--year==05)year=99;
```

```
                break;
```

```
            case 2:
```

```
                if(--month==0)month=12;
```

```
                break;
```

```
            case 3:
```

```
                if(--day==0)day=31;
```

```
if(--day_name==-
```

```
1)day_name = 6;
```

```
break;
```

```
case 4:
```

```
if(--sec==1)sec=59;
```

```
break;
```

```
case 5:
```

```
if(--min==1)min=59;
```

```
break;
```

```
case 6:
```

```
if(--hour==1)hour=12; flag1=!flag1;
```

```
break;
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

```
while(!P3_4){}
```

```
}
```

```
if(disp_pos!=0){  
    flag=1;}  
else{  
    flag=0;  
}  
if(!P3_6){  
    delay(30);  
    if(!P3_6){  
        disp_pos++;  
        if(disp_pos>6)disp_pos=0;  
    }  
    while(!P3_6){;}  
    delay(300);  
}
```

```
        //P3 = day_name | 0xf8;
    }
}
```

4.4 Software/Hardware Integration

The software is written to acknowledge the hardware components, which is burn into the microcontroller. This software is access via the input buttons as it is depressed.

Having done this, then as the program runs, it acknowledges all other peripheral devices. The microcontroller has connected to it a interface the 74LS138 Decoder which sends a logic 1 or 0 signal to the light emitting diodes (LEDS) which in turns light up the corresponding LED that display either Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday, etc.

CHAPTER FIVE: TESTING

5.1 System Testing and Integration

After the design and implementation phase, the system built has to be tested for Durability, Efficiency, and Effectiveness and also ascertain if there is need to modify this design. The system was first assembled using a breadboard. All components were properly inserted into the breadboard from whence some tests were carried out at various stages.

To ensure proper functioning of components' expected data, the components were tested using a digital multimeter (DMM). Resistors were tested to ensure that they were within the tolerance value. Faulty resistors were discarded .The 78LS05 voltage regulator was also tested, the resulting output was 5.02v which is just a deviation of 0.20v from the expected result of 5.00v.The LEDs were tested to ensure that they were all working properly.

5.2 Test plan and Test data

This chapter entails an overall system testing of the integrated design of the voltage measurement device. The testing and integration is done to ensure that the design is functioning properly as expected thereby enabling one or even intended users for which the project was targeted for, appreciate its

implementation and equally approaches used in the design and integration of the various modules of the project.

However, this involves checks made to ensure that all the various units and subsystems function adequately. Also there has to be a good interface existing between the input/output unit subsystems.

When the totality of the modules was integrated together, the system was created and all modules and sections responded to as specified in the design through the power supply delivering into the system designed.

5.2.1 Components Test

Similar components like resistors were packed together. Other components includes capacitor, preset switches, transformer, diodes (rectifier) LED, transistor, voltage regulator etc

Reference was made to resistor colour code data sheet to ascertain the expected values of resistors used. Each resistor was tested and the value read and recorded. Also for transistor test the DMM was switched to the diode range with the symbol

 The collector, base and emitter junctions were tested in the following order. The collector, emitter and base pins were gotten from the data analysis on power transistor.

Table 5.1 Test for Transistor

	Black probe	Red probe
1 st test on pins	Collector	Base
2 nd test on pins	Emitter	Base

5.2.2 System Test

The system was powered and operated upon using several possibilities. They include depressing more than one button at the same time and noting the output responses of the system hardware. The system allows only one input at a time and gives the voice output along side flashing the corresponding LED.

5.2.3 Transformer Test (Step-Down

Expectedly, the transformer was rated 240v/12v,300mA.From the mains power supply , the primary coil received 220v input; the output was measured to b e 13.75v using a DMM.

Test data on transformer has it that the resistance of the primary windings for step down transformer is higher than that of the secondary side. This was ascertained.

5.2.4 Other Tests

Light emitting diode (LED) emits rays when forward biased .For capacitors the DMM was switched to the 22uf range and the capacitors were inserted into the slot provided for it by the meter. Other test carried out include depressing of the calendar and time set button one after the other; observing the output in the seven segment display. Also the increasing and decreasing button is also depressed to see if there is increment and decrement on the other hand of the segment display. Finally the alarm button is depressed to activate the alarm, when the alarm was activated the alarm indicator lighted to show that the alarm system is armed.

5.3 EXPERIMENTED RESULT VS ACTUAL RESULT

Table 5.2 Experimented Value/ Actual value

COMPONENTS	EXPERIMENTED VALUE	ACTUAL VALUE	UNIT	TOLERANCE
Resistor	10000	10000	Ω	5%
	2000	2000	Ω	
	220	218	Ω	
	10000	9980	Ω	
Capacitor	10	10.20	μf	
	10	10.15	ρf	
	30	29.82	ρf	
Transistor	R_{be} 520	550	Ω	
	R_{bc} 510	548	Ω	
Transformer voltage	12Vac @ 240Vac	13.2 @	V	
	input	210	V	
Regulator	5.00	5.02	V	

5.4 Performance Evaluation

From the table above, shows the range between the expected value and the actual value can be tolerated. As a result of this the drift in expected value has no critical effect on the system design since the result current range was not also exceeded, also the operational voltage range was not exceeded.

CHAPTER SIX: SUMMARY

6.1 Summary and Conclusion

This section of this project report forms the concluding part of the write up and takes a look at some of the problems encountered during the progressive job on the system and also brings in suggestions for further improvement and/or enhancement for the system design.

6.2 Summary of Achievement

The design and development of this project has really been challenging, as I have been faced with choices far beyond what I expected. But in the long run the result paid off.

After the complete design of the system, the deviation between the expected result and the actual result was very close. The performance and efficiency was beyond expectation and from every ramification, the design of the microcontroller based digital calendar was a success.

6.3 Problems Encountered and Solution

During the course of the design of this system, there were series of problems which came in the way of achieving the design goals of this project, most of them where over come via share troubleshooting, in some cases some parts require redesigning and the software debugging also created a bit of a problem.

One major set back of this project is the availability of components required to build the hardware of the system. In most cases I had to look through electrical catalogs to obtain replacements of some of the components which are not available in the market.

After developing the software for the microcontroller, it was very difficult to find a firm/individual to help program the chip (burning the embedded software on to the chip). This posed serious problem as it brought about delay in the design time and it was also costly, this also affected the overall cost of the system.

The final packaging of the design was also another trouble, as this actually caused problems on the circuit board. Such problems include partial contact within the circuit board, between components and also with the wiring. This was actually one of the most challenging aspects of the circuit implementation phase. Due to this fact, there was a lot of soldering and de-soldering to ensure that the circuit was well implemented.

6.4 Suggestions for further improvement

It will be more appreciated if the system is designed to have integrated voice output playback. The size of the digital calendar and clock should be reduced for portability sake.

6.5 Conclusion

Going through the planning, flow process, design and software implementation the system had really been a tough one; but on the whole it has been a chance to show case a little bit of craftsmanship.

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APPENDIX A

SYSTEM COMPONENTS LIST

1. Vero Board
2. Connection Wire
3. Seven Segment Display
4. Light Emitting Diode
5. Soldering Iron
6. AC Cord
7. 240 / 12v, 200 mA Transformer
8. Rectifier Diodes
9. 2200uf /25V Capacitor
10. 10uf 16V Capacitor
11. 30pf capacitor
12. Resistors
13. 7805 Voltage Regulator
14. Touch Buttons
15. 16 MHz crystal oscillator
16. AT89C51 Micro controller

17. 74LS138 Decoder

18. IC Base Socket (40 pins)

19. IC Base Socket (16 pins)

20. Transistors

21. Battery

APPENDIX B

COMPONENTS COST ANALYSIS TABLE

S/N	COMPONENTS	QUANTITY	UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY PRICE
1	220V/12V,300mA		300	300
2	Rectifier Diodes	1	40	40
3	2200uf/25V	1	30	30
4	10uf/16V	1	30	30
5	30pf	2	30	60
6	10k resistor	6	5	30
7	220Ω resistor	14	5	70
8	4.7k resistor	1	5	5
9	2k resistor	14	5	70

10	LEDS	7	5	35
11	78LS05	1	60	60
12	Touch Button	6	30	180
13	16MHz Oscillator	1	70	70
14	AT89C51	1	1700	1700
15	74LS138	1	150	150
16	IC Base (40 pins)	1	60	60

S/N	COMPONENTS	QUANTITY	UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY PRICE
17	IC Base (20 pins)	1	50	50
18	Connection Wires	15 yards	150	150
19	Vero Board	1	180	180
20	Seven Segment Display	6	120	720
21	Soldering Lead	6 yards	20	120
22	AC Cord	1	60	60
23	Battery	1	60	60
24	Casing	1	1800	1800

TOTAL COSTING _____ **# 6,255**

APPENDIX C

CIRCUIT COMPONENTS LAYOUT

APPENDIX D

CIRCUIT WIRING OF AT89C51

Uc / 1.....Segment “a” of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 2.....Segment “b” of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 3Segment “c” of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 4Segment “d” of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 5Segment “e” of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 6Segment “f” of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 7Segment “g” of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 8Alarm set

Uc / 9+ve of Capacitor 10uf / 16V

Uc / 10.....Increment Button

Uc / 11.....Enter Button

Uc / 12.....Dot of time segment

Uc / 13.....Pin 1 of 74SL138

Uc / 14Pin 2 of 74SL138

Uc / 15.....Pin 3 of 74SL138

Uc / 38 Segment "b" of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 39 Segment "a" of seven segment of calendar

Uc / 40Vcc +5v

CIRCUIT WIRING OF 74LS138 DECODER

Pin 1..... Uc / 13

Pin 2 Uc / 14

Pin 3 Uc / 15

Pin 4,5,8 Gnd

Pin 6Vcc

Pin 9 LED

Pin 10..... LED

Pin 11LED

Pin 12LED

Pin 13LED

Pin 14LED

Pin 15LED

Pin 16Vcc +5v

APPENDIX F

SYSTEM SOURCE CODE (ATMEL 89C51 MICROCONTROLLER

USING C LANGUAGE)

```
#include "at89x51.h"
```

```
code unsigned char
```

```
digit[16]={0x40,0x79,0x24,0x30,0x19,0x12,0x02,0x78,0,0x10,0x08,0x03,0x46,0x21,0x06,0x0e};
```

```
code unsigned int
```

```
dec[]={0x0,0x1,0x2,0x3,0x4,0x5,0x6,0x7,0x8,0x9,0x10,0x11,0x12,0x13,0x14,0x15,0x16,0x17,0x18,0x19,0x20,0x21,0x22,0x23,0x24,0x25,0x26,0x27,0x28,0x29,0x30,0x31,0x32,0x33,0x34,0x35,0x36,0x37,0x38,0x39,0x40,0x41,0x42,0x43,0x44,0x45,0x46,0x47,0x48,0x49,0x50,0x51,0x52,0x53,0x54,0x55,0x56,0x57,0x58,0x59,0x60,0x61,0x62,0x63,0x64,0x65,0x66,0x67,0x68,0x69,0x70,0x71,0x72,0x73,0x74,0x75,0x76,0x77,0x78,0x79,0x80,0x81,0x82,0x83,0x84,0x85,0x86,0x87,0x88,0x89,0x90,0x91,0x92,0x93,0x94,0x95,0x96,0x97,0x98,0x99
```

```

};

volatile unsigned char
buffer,buffer2,display_buffer1,display_buffer3,display_buffer4,display_buffer5
;

volatile unsigned char
display_buffer2,display_buffer6,display_buffer7,i,x,y,show;

volatile unsigned char data1,data2,data3,data4,set_pos,disp_pos;

bit flag,over;

char sec,min,hour,day,month;

unsigned int year,del;

//delay function:

void delay(int pause)
{
while (!(pause==0))
{
    pause--;

_asm;          // 1ms assembly code(for 18Mhz crystal)

mov r6,#3     // adjust to crystal frequency

mov r7,#215

```

```

00111$:

djnz r7,00111$

djnz r6,00111$

_endasm;

}

}

//;;;;;;;;;;;;;Display Functin;;;;;;;;;;;;;

void display(void) interrupt 1

{

TR0=0;          //disable timer

if((del>400)&&(disp_pos==0)){

    del=1;

    //=====running the normal clock loop=====

    sec++;

    if(sec==60){

        sec=0;

        min++;

        if(min==60){

            min=0;

```

```
hour++;

if(hour==24){

    hour=0;

    day++;

    switch(month){

//jan

case 1:

if(day==32){

    day=1;

    month++;}

    break;

//feb

case 2:

if((year%4)==0){

    if(day==30){

        day=1;

        month++;}

        break;

    }

}
```

```
else{  
    if(day==29){  
        day=1;  
        month++;}  
    }  
    break;  
  
//mar  
  
case 3:  
  
if(day==32){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
    break;  
  
//apr  
  
case 4:  
  
if(day==31){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
    break;  
  
//may
```

```
case 5:  
  
if(day==32){  
  
    day=1;  
  
    month++;}  
  
    break;
```

```
//june
```

```
case 6:  
  
if(day==31){  
  
    day=1;  
  
    month++;}  
  
    break;
```

```
//july
```

```
case 7:  
  
if(day==32){  
  
    day=1;  
  
    month++;}  
  
    break;
```

```
//aug
```

```
case 8:
```

```
if(day==32){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
break;  
  
//sep  
case 9:  
if(day==31){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
break;  
  
//oct  
case 10:  
if(day==32){  
    day=1;  
    month++;}  
break;  
  
//nov  
case 11:  
if(day==31){
```

```
        day=1;
        month++;}
        break;
//dec
case 12:
if(day==32){
        day=1;
        month=1;
        year++;
        if(year==100)year=0;}
        break;
default:
break;
}
}
}
if(i>7){
```

```
display_buffer1=dec[day];  
display_buffer2=dec[month];  
display_buffer3=dec[year/100];  
display_buffer4=dec[year%100];  
display_buffer5=dec[hour];  
display_buffer6=dec[min];  
display_buffer7=dec[sec];  
i=0;}
```

```
switch(i){
```

```
case 1:
```

```
P2_0=0;
```

```
buffer=display_buffer1 & 0x0f; // show first character
```

```
if(flag&&(disp_pos!=1)){P1=0x3f;}
```

```
else{P1=digit[buffer];}
```

```
buffer=display_buffer5 & 0x0f; // show p first
```

```
character
```

```
if(flag&&(disp_pos!=4)){P0=0x3f;}
```

```
else{P0=digit[buffer];}
```

```
P3=i;P2_0=1
```

```

break;

case 0:

P2_0=0;

buffer=(display_buffer1>>4) & 0x0f;           // show second character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=1)){P1=0x3f;}

else{P1=digit[buffer];}

P3=i;P2_0=1;

buffer=(display_buffer5>>4) & 0x0f;           // show second character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=4)){P0=0x3f;}

else{P0=digit[buffer];}

P3=i;P2_0=1;

break;

case 3:

P2_0=0;

buffer=display_buffer2 & 0x0f;                 // show first character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=2)){P1=0x3f;}

else{P1=digit[buffer];}

buffer=display_buffer6 & 0x0f;                 // show p first
character

```

```

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=5)){P0=0x3f;}

else{P0=digit[buffer];}

P3=i;P2_0=1;

break;

case 2:

P2_0=0;

buffer=(display_buffer2>>4) & 0x0f;           // show second character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=2)){P1=0x3f;}

else{P1=digit[buffer];}

P3=i;P2_0=1;

buffer=(display_buffer6>>4) & 0x0f;           // show second character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=5)){P0=0x3f;}

else{P0=digit[buffer];}

P3=i;P2_0=1;

break;

case 5:

P2_0=0;

buffer=display_buffer3 & 0x0f;                // show first character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=3)){P1=0x3f;}

```

```

else{P1=digit[buffer];}

buffer=display_buffer7 & 0x0f;           // show p first
character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=6)){P0=0x3f;}

else{P0=digit[buffer];}

P3=i;P2_0=1;

break;

case 4:

P2_0=0;

buffer=(display_buffer3>>4) & 0x0f;     // show second character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=3)){P1=0x3f;}

else{P1=digit[buffer];}

buffer=(display_buffer7>>4) & 0x0f;     // show second character

if(flag&&(disp_pos!=6)){P0=0x3f;}

else{P0=digit[buffer];}

P3=i;P2_0=1;

break;

case 7:

P2_0=0;

```

```

    buffer=display_buffer4 & 0x0f;                // show first character

    if(flag&&(disp_pos!=3)){P1=0x3f;}

    else{P1=digit[buffer];}

    P3=i;P2_0=1;

    break;

    case 6:

    P2_0=0;

    buffer=(display_buffer4>>4) & 0x0f;        // show second character

    if(flag&&(disp_pos!=3)){P1=0x3f;}

    else{P1=digit[buffer];}

    P3=i;P2_0=1;

    break;

    default:

    break;

}

    i++; del++;

    TH0=180;                // load timer

    TL0=240;

```

```

TR0=1;                //enable timer
}

void main(void){

    TMOD=0; //choose timer mode

    ET0=1;           //enable timer interupt
    EA=1;           //enable global interupt

    TR0=1;          //run timer

    flag=i=0;      //intitalize variables

    del=1;set_pos=disp_pos=0;

    sec=59;min=20;hour=11;day=31;month=8;year=2006;

    //P0=P1=x=0;

    while(1){

        if(!P2_2){

            delay(30);

            if(!P2_2){

                switch(disp_pos){

                    case 1:

                        if(++day>31)day=1;

                        break;

```

case 2:

if(++month>12)month=1;

break;

case 3:

if(++year > 2100)year=2006;

break;

case 4:

if(++hour > 23)hour=0;

break;

case 5:

if(++min > 59)min=0;

break;

case 6:

if(++sec > 59)sec=0;

break;

}

}

while(!P2_2){}

}

```
if(!P2_3){  
    delay(30);  
    if(!P2_3){  
        switch(dispos){  
            case 1:  
                if(--day==0)day=31;  
                break  
            case 2:  
                if(--month==0)month=12;  
                break;  
            case 3:  
                if(--year==2005)year=2100;  
                break;  
            case 4:  
                if(--hour==-1)hour=23;  
                break;  
            case 5:  
                if(--min==-1)min=59;  
                break;
```

```
        case 6:
            if(--sec==0)sec=59;
            break;
        }
    }
    while(!P2_3){;}
    }
    if(dispos!=0){
        flag=1;}
    else{
        flag=0;
    }
    if(!P2_1){
        delay(30);
        if(!P2_1){
            disp_pos++;
            if(disp_pos>6)disp_pos=0;
        }
        while(!P2_1){;}
    }
```

```
        delay(300);
    }
}
}
```

APPENDIX G
SYSTEM USERS GUIDE

PROCEDURES

Step 1: Plug the power cord to AC main

Step 11: Switch the power button ON

Step 111: Press either time, calendar or alarm button to activate the corresponding parameter to be set

Step 1V: Use the increment or decrement button to set parameters

Step V: Then press the enter button to display either the time, calendar or alarm.

APPENDIX I

ATMEL 89C51 MICROCONTROLLER INSTRUCTION SET

Mnemonic		Description	Byte	Oscillator Period
RR	A	Rotate Accumulator Right	1	12
RRC	A	Rotate Accumulator Right through the Carry	1	12
SWAP	A	Swap nibbles within the Accumulator	1	12
DATA TRANSFER				
MOV	A,R _n	Move register to Accumulator	1	12
MOV	A,direct	Move direct byte to Accumulator	2	12
MOV	A,@R _i	Move indirect RAM to Accumulator	1	12
MOV	A,#data	Move immediate data to Accumulator	2	12
MOV	R _n ,A	Move Accumulator to register	1	12
MOV	R _n ,direct	Move direct byte to register	2	24
MOV	R _n ,#data	Move immediate data to register	2	12
MOV	direct,A	Move Accumulator to direct byte	2	12
MOV	direct,R _n	Move register to direct byte	2	24
MOV	direct,direct	Move direct byte to direct	3	24
MOV	direct,@R _i	Move indirect RAM to direct byte	2	24
MOV	direct,#data	Move immediate data to direct byte	3	24
MOV	@R _i ,A	Move Accumulator to indirect RAM	1	12
MOV	@R _i ,direct	Move direct byte to indirect RAM	2	24
MOV	@R _i ,#data	Move immediate data to indirect RAM	2	12
MOV	DPTR,#data16	Load Data Pointer with a 16-bit constant	3	24
MOVC	A,@A+DPTR	Move Code byte relative to DPTR to Acc	1	24
MOVC	A,@A+PC	Move Code byte relative to PC to Acc	1	24
MOVX	A,@R _i	Move External RAM (8-bit addr) to Acc	1	24
DATA TRANSFER (continued)				

Mnemonic		Description	Byte	Oscillator Period
LOGICAL OPERATIONS				
ANL	A,R _n	AND Register to Accumulator	1	12
ANL	A,direct	AND direct byte to Accumulator	2	12
ANL	A,@R _i	AND indirect RAM to Accumulator	1	12
ANL	A,#data	AND immediate data to Accumulator	2	12
ANL	direct,A	AND Accumulator to direct byte	2	12
ANL	direct,#data	AND immediate data to direct byte	3	24
ORL	A,R _n	OR register to Accumulator	1	12
ORL	A,direct	OR direct byte to Accumulator	2	12
ORL	A,@R _i	OR indirect RAM to Accumulator	1	12
ORL	A,#data	OR immediate data to Accumulator	2	12
ORL	direct,A	OR Accumulator to direct byte	2	12
ORL	direct,#data	OR immediate data to direct byte	3	24
XRL	A,R _n	Exclusive-OR register to Accumulator	1	12
XRL	A,direct	Exclusive-OR direct byte to Accumulator	2	12
XRL	A,@R _i	Exclusive-OR indirect RAM to Accumulator	1	12
XRL	A,#data	Exclusive-OR immediate data to Accumulator	2	12
XRL	direct,A	Exclusive-OR Accumulator to direct byte	2	12
XRL	direct,#data	Exclusive-OR immediate data to direct byte	3	24
CLR	A	Clear Accumulator	1	12
CPL	A	Complement Accumulator	1	12
RL	A	Rotate Accumulator Left	1	12
RLC	A	Rotate Accumulator Left through the Carry	1	12
LOGICAL OPERATIONS (continued)				

Mnemonic		Description	Byte	Oscillator Period
ACALL	addr11	Absolute Subroutine Call	2	24
LCALL	addr16	Long Subroutine Call	3	24
RET		Return from Subroutine	1	24
RETI		Return from interrupt	1	24
AJMP	addr11	Absolute Jump	2	24
LJMP	addr16	Long Jump	3	24
SJMP	rel	Short Jump (relative addr)	2	24
JMP	@A+DPTR	Jump indirect relative to the DPTR	1	24
JZ	rel	Jump if Accumulator is Zero	2	24
JNZ	rel	Jump if Accumulator is Not Zero	2	24
CJNE	A,direct,rel	Compare direct byte to Acc and Jump if Not Equal	3	24
CJNE	A,#data,rel	Compare immediate to Acc and Jump if Not Equal	3	24
CJNE	R _n ,#data,rel	Compare immediate to register and Jump if Not Equal	3	24
CJNE	@R _i ,#data,rel	Compare immediate to indirect and Jump if Not Equal	3	24
DJNZ	R _n ,rel	Decrement register and Jump if Not Zero	2	24
DJNZ	direct,rel	Decrement direct byte and Jump if Not Zero	3	24
NOP		No Operation	1	12

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